

Anyang

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Anyang is a modern municipal in northern Henan province of China. In the late 19th century, an accidental discovery of inscribed oracle bones at Anyang led to the beginning of the archaeological excavations in 1929. Nearly-a-century archaeological discoveries and inscribed oracle bones confirm that Anyang was the location of the ancient ruin of Yin, dated to 14th - 11th century BCE. For more than 250 years, Anyang was a political and religious centre of Shang Kingdom (ca. 1600 - 1046 BCE), the earliest known state that controlled the lands of Yellow River and Yangtze River valleys. Divinations by processing turtle shells and ox bones and then application of incised texts onto shells and bones after divining had been a major state affair exclusive to royal houses and elites. Shang people worship the Di or God literally in English, as a supernatural being, thus the Heavily Above. The Di, or Heavily Above, could be represented by deceased kings, thus ancestral worships, as tradition of Chinese ritual since prehistoric periods, was a core of Shang's ritual endeavours. Shang ritual process for state affairs from wars to marriage, have produced oracle bones as documentation. Inscribed oracle bones, survived nearly 200,000 pieces, provide the first written history of religious activity in China. Archaeologically, Anyang is well known for its abundance of ritual bronze vessels, that can be viewed in major museums worldwide. The ritual bronze vessels were evident that Shang rituals were in wide various forms and objectives. Shang people worshiped gods or supernatural beings from mountains and rivers, as well as natural phenomena like rains, winds, thunders. Anyang yields a wider variety of archaeological evidences suggesting that it was a largest and populated city in East Asia at the time for over 250 years.

Date Range: 1300 BCE - 1046 BCE

Region: Anyang

Region tags: China, Henan Province

territory of Shang Dynasty region: Hebei, Hennan, Hubei, Anhui, Shandong province

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Goldin, Paul R. (editor) 2018 Routledge Handbook of Early Chinese History. Routledge, London and New York.
- Source 2: Shen, Chen 2002 Anyang and Sanxingdui: Unveriling the Mysteries of Ancient Chinese Civilizations. Royal Ontario Museum Press, Toronto.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Anyang>

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/place/Anyang-China>

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Anyang is an archaeological site that was first excavated by the Institute of History and Philology, Academic Sinica, Republic of China before 1949, than continued by the Institute of Archaeology, Chinese Academic of Social Science, People's Republic of China

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1929 - present

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Anyang Archaeology

Notes: Permanent Archaeology Workstation Unit from the Institute of Archaeology, Chinese Academy of Social Science, China is responsible for continuous excavations of Anyang sites in response to urban development plan. Before 1949, excavations at Anyang were carried out by archaeologists and scientists from the Institute of History and Philosophy, Sinica Academics of Republic of China.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: River Valley - Heng River a tribute to the Yellow River

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Notes: The place was built as a politic-religious centre of Shang Kingdom, including structures like palaces, temples, alters, factories, cemeteries, and occupational buildings

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: Anyang is a designate /inscribe World Heritage Site, so there is a defined prediction boundary between the site and the urban fabric

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The site, found first identified and excavated, was at vicinity of populated township in early 20th century, but now is a part of modern municipal with a population of more than 5 million.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: The place was situated in the rural setting when it was discovered in 1920s. With urbanization and city development since later 20th century, the place is now completely within the city limit

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Notes: a high-speed train going through the city, with a major station, that connects Beijing and Zhengzhou. It took 2 hours from Beijing, and 1 hour from Zhengzhou, capital city of Henan province.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

Notes: Anyang religious structures consisted of multiple functional sites across the ruin

↳ One single feature

–Other [specify]: architectural complex

↳ A group of structures:

– No

Notes: see above note

– Yes

Notes: Different functional religious sites are part of different groups, not single group, like temples, palaces, sacrificial pits, alter, residential buildings, and open sites.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: Structures could have built in different time-period over the 250 years of royal occupations of Shang Kingdom, for different purposes. Some structures could have been as part of a single design/construction stage at a certain period

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

Notes: Again, different functional/purposed religious features belongs to different groups like temples, palaces, sacrificial pits, cemeteries, etc.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: Could be for some group of features, but not for all.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: see note above

– No

Notes: Shang's rulers governed the kingdom by extensive rituals and religious activities - e.g. division. All features and structures are centred to state administration. There are relations, structurally and functionally, between features, but they did not belong each other like a single complex. If yes, they are part of a large administrative centre.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Sacrificial

– Social

Notes: Ritual taking place when divining for wedding, hosting guests, the likes.

– Memorial

Notes: Rituals taking place a festival for deceased ancestors

– Healing

Notes: Rituals taking place for healing

– Political

Notes: Divination ritual was a must for state affairs and wars, and all decision making

– Worship

Notes: For Anyang, the groups of features /structures are multi-purpose. so they include worship, sacrificial, memorial, healing, political, social, praying.

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Buried

↳ With ritually deposited medium/material:

This might consists of pure sand, or a medium that has been consecrated.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–Other [specify]: all of the above

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

–Human-caused accident

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity
– More than once

↳ In modernity
– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: Gods

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: God of Heavenly Above (Shang4 Di, or Di, 上帝 ; God of Four-Lands (Shi Fang Shen 四方神) ; God of Wind (Feng Shen 风神) ; God of Rain (Yu Shen 雨神) ; God of Cloud (Yun Shen 云神) ; God of Sun (Ri Shen 日神)

Notes: In addition, occasionally, worshiping Thunder, River, Mountain, Earth, the like

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: All king's deceased ancestors are treated as gods

↳ Is it a cenotaph:
– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:
– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Notes: Ritual function taking place at family shrine/temple; deceased ancestors (including kings) were given names of temples, the only names on the writing records.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Given its multi-purposes of places, some places might be commissioned, but some might not.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Notes: different groups of people may required for different purposes of structures.

↳ Groups:

– Corvee labourers

– Slaves

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

Notes: Many structures were originated as the result of divine intervention, like palaces/temples where divination took place

↳ Specify

– Revelation occurred through divination

– No

Notes: Some structures, like cemeteries and sacrificial pits, are not originated by the divine intervention, but it must have been related to divination

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

- ↳ Specify
 - Oracle
 - Prophecy
 - Other [specify]: establishing a governing centre of politic and religious system

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

- Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

- Other [specify]: Divine
- Other [specify]: administration

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

- Field doesn't know

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

- Yes

- ↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:
 - Field doesn't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

- No

Notes: But there were oversized and overpowered underground tomb structures, that might have required labor and resources similar to pyramids.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Field doesn't know

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Field doesn't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

Notes: Stone is not primarily building materials, but applied to some components of the buildings

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Plant

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Field doesn't know

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Assuming yes, but no archaeological evidence to indicate

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Taotie, an imagery animal faces appears mostly on bronze casts, bone carvings, stone carvings, etc.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - Yes
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - No
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Humans
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human narratives
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: none

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: The place includes many tombs/burials belongs to different classes from royal members to

comers, all being practiced sacrificial rituals

– No

Notes: The place included not only tombs/burials, but also temples, altars, shrines, palaces, where rituals were preformed

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

Notes: The place includes many structures such as temples, shrines, palaces, where the worship of the dead taking place

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– Yes

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to the elements:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other intensive (time/resources expended) treatment [Specify]:

–Other [specify]: Ceremonial event

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– Yes

↳ Human:

– Yes

↳ How many humans are present:

– Number of human sacrifices: 1 - 100+

↳ Out-group humans are sacrificed:

– Yes

Notes: captives, specifically Qiang people

↳ In-group humans are sacrificed:

– Yes

↳ Other humans are sacrificed:

–Other [specify]: Royal family members

↳ Animal:

– Yes

Notes: Including domesticated animals specific for ritual purpose, like ox, sheep, dog.

↳ How many animals are present:

– Number of animals: 1 - 100+

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Persona adornment, drink and food offering

↳ Other

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: the formal burials are arranged by ranks of clans and nobility ranking, size and scope of the burials vary accordingly

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Di 帝, or Shang Di 上帝, appeared in oracle bone divining texts, referred to the Heavenly Above. Di administrated other gods including God of Four-lands 四方神, God of Wing 风神, God of Cloud 云神, and God of Sun 日神

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: only in reference in the oracle bone

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

Notes: The high god 上帝 is not, but other gods under the high god may be, like God of Earth.

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Yes or No, early kings were worshipped in the same way as the high god 上帝, but not all kings were treated the same ways.

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: many unclear identity from oracle bone scripts

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: Shang people focused on oracle bone divining practice

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: kings and diviners

↳ Only through monarch:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: thought ancestral worship

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession:
– No

↳ Through divination practices:
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:
– Yes

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: through ritual performance and ritual objects

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: through ritual performance and ritual objects depicting imagery and unknown animals

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:
 - Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes

- ↳ In dreams:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes

- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - Yes

- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: yes, likely through dragon and imagery bird

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: Dog, ox, goat/sheep

Notes: Domestic and special treatment animals

Are there human sacrifices:

– Yes

Adults

– Yes

Is biological sex available from evidence:

– Male

– Female

Children

– Yes

Is biological sex available from evidence:

– Male

– Female

Foreigners and/or slaves

– Yes

Is biological sex available from evidence:

– Male

– Female

↳ Elites

– Yes

↳

Is biological sex available from evidence:

– Female

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: human sacrifices were common at Anyang Society depending on the status of clans and nobility ranking.

↳

Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– Yes [specify]: Separate burials

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– Field doesn't know

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳

Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳

Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳

Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳

Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

↳

Other

– Other [specify]: size and scope of material offering varied depending on the status of clans and nobility ranking

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

- ↳ By all the community
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: Assuming mandatory for members of clans and relatives

- ↳ By specific individuals
 - Yes [specify]: Diviner / Kings, leaders of clans
 - Notes: Assuming this worship and sacrifice are at state and royal family

Is maintenance of the place performed:

- Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

- Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

- Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

- Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

- Yes

Notes: Divination at Shang Culture is the most prominent state and community affairs of all aspects. King, sometimes acted as diviner, and his designated diviner would process and read the oracle for decision-making.

- ↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

- Yes

- ↳ Species

- Yes [specify]: Ox and turtle

- ↳ Part
 - Yes [specify]: Bone

- ↳ Remains are consumed:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: Bone were processed and treated before divining, and preserved and buried after divining.

- ↳ Remains are disposed of:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Divination through human communication:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Is a human being the vehicle for the oracle:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Diviners, sometimes kings, asked for divination-making questions.

 - ↳ Is a human being the interpreter of the oracle:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Diviners, sometimes kings, would do.

 - ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified sex/gender:
 - Field doesn't know

 - ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified ethnicity:
 - Field doesn't know

 - ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified class:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Maybe more than one class, but mostly are designated diviners, or kings

 - ↳ Is sex-deprivation required:
 - Field doesn't know

 - ↳ Are intoxicants required:
 - No

↳ Physical ordeal required:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:
– No

↳ Divination through non-living material:
– Bones

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: through ancestral worship

Is healing present/practiced at this place:
– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Although divination is the most important ritual in Shang culture, other rituals associated with worships to gods, natures, ancestors, and deceased.

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
– specify: Tens to hundreds?

Notes: The field doesn't know, because there is no written record for specific participants, but there were description how the ritual were preformed that could privilege clues for scopes of the scale.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
– specify: Annual or event-specific (wedding, outing, hunting etc)

Notes: Towards the end of Shang dynasty, a regular and recycled ritual preformed were regulated.

- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: The diviner, 贞人 Zeng

- ↳ Present full time
 - Yes
- ↳ Present part time
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
 - No
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
 - Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Yes

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: Anyang is a place of royal administrative center

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– No

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Notes: this place has many locations to different communities

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Yes

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– Yes

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Industrial production, like pottery making, bronze casting, bone carving, jade carving

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Writing appeared on bronze casting indicating identities of clan, and others.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Field doesn't know

Bibliography

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